

A STUDY OF TECHNOLOGY CAN ENHANCE TEACHING SCHOOL EDUCATION LEARNING EXPERIENCE

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Introduction

In the present time, technology has turned into an integral piece of our lives. Consistently there is new gadget or software that makes lives less demanding. Making lives less demanding isn't, in any case, the main job that the technology plays in our lives. In fact, it is assuming key job in improving each part of life. Technology has opened new ways to immaculate aspects of life and has immensely influenced each field of human life. The field of education isn't an exemption. It is assuming an expanding job in the field of education. Technology in educational field is changing the customary job of the partners of education. New information and communication technology has presented numerous adjustments in the present educational framework. Intuitive advances have influenced the very idea of teaching and learning. Technology offers the chance to change the jobs that instructors and understudies have customarily played. As technology progresses, it is utilized to profit understudies of any age in learning process. Technology utilized in classroom encourages understudies to retain the material. Projection screens connected to PC enable understudies to see their notes rather than basically tuning in to an educator who is conveying an address. Technology has likewise progressed to enable kids to learn even before they have begun school. Educational computer games and software for youthful children help them plan for school and sometimes get a head begin in their education. Information and communication

advancements are helping in changing the educational condition. These advances are electronic and automated gadget and related human intuitive materials that empower the client to utilize them for a wide scope of teaching and learning forms. These advances incorporate PCs, video, TV, sensors, interface boxes, the internet, telecommunication, satellite associations and every one of the software and the materials which assist the educators with using them to show their students. So also, software is utilized to enhance class educational modules. There are programs which give think about inquiries, exercises and even test and tests outside the classroom. Technology has additionally progressed toward becoming piece of numerous educational modules; understudies use PCs to make introductions and use internet to look points for papers and expositions .They figure out how to utilize the technology accessible to them in classrooms or at home. This guarantees after investigations that they will almost certainly utilize the technology in a work setting, which may put them in front of other people who did not approach specific technology or software in their very own school setting. produced with this method (htt) (Abdul Razzak, April 2017).

In case the argument is presented that educators are unhappy with technology it has been seen that in that situation point load desires from technology are observed. Nevertheless, putting asidethe perspective of such educators, Naimova haspointed at the perspective of managers as one of the variables capable of influencing educational technology’s appropriation. According to Naimova in case of managers if there is absence ofsupport from their side, it can lead to delayed in the utilization of technology in the area of study hall Nazimova, Research and Collection of Data (Naimova, Factors affecting the implementation of instructional technology in the Second Language classroom, 2008) (Jaflah, 2012).

Scope of Technology in School Education

Today’s age is the age of technology. Technology can be seen in every walk of life. It is responsible to bring in a drastic change in life. It has brought speed in our work, efficiency, advancement and excellence in our lives. In the aspect of teaching or learning, it has made it more complete or inclusive as well as simple; also students have been able to display more informative in a calculative lesser time. In a broader manner it includes progressive expansion, implementation and assessment of structures and procedures. The year 2020, has shown a drastic change in the way of studying and learning, in the whole World. The schools, colleges and Universities have gone online, which is a new way of studying. The present situation has taught the educators the new norm of teaching and explaining. The understudies

have also accepted the new norm and are dedicatedly involved in learning. The entire world was caught unaware about the situation, since studies have to go uninterrupted and learning should be a continuous. The understudies are taking utmost care to capture the desired learning outcomes and explain the new topics with clear and concise pedagogy. With the present pandemic condition, E-Schooling is the only way to equip teachers for a new normal. Schools are getting transformed into screens time. u

MAJOR CHARACTERISTICS OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY

Discipline

ET is all set to discipline the understudies to face challenges of the near and distant future. The world has already set into the optimum utilization of data, IT and systems of state of the art communication such as internet based programs or web-based learning, digital lessons or online learning through live virtual classrooms etc.

Usage as per technological advancements

The growth of ET depends wholly on technological advancement in the field of science. Innovations that are scientifically and technologically oriented with the main aim to resolve challenges are adopted by the educational institutions. Developments scientific understanding leads to the introduction of advanced, complicated and sophisticated devices.

Modifying the education system

Problems can be identified in the educational sector, which can be easily resolved by ET. ET basically targets at upgrading the systems in the area of education. Useful and result oriented communication can be built up between the understudies and their educators, so that fulfill all learning objectives.

Research based

Social sciences, can be best be used by ET, also that it is applied to other field of education.

Effective classroom management

Technology when applied in classroom effectively and efficiently can bring in desired results. Care has to be taken that the usage is should be time bound. The system approach and the objectives to be achieved should be from both sides the teacher and student.

Mass media Communication

ET can be used to easily provide education to a great number of students simultaneously. This system supersedes all barriers such as an individual's drawbacks of languages known, place of living, economical status or social background.

A process

ET is a course to realize an end but not an end to itself. Improved class performance is the result or output or an end in the process of delivering education. Here the input given to the students by using Education Technology in the teaching- learning process is the method under focus.

Wider scope

As stated previously, the scope of ET is not just restricted to use of educational gadgets in classrooms for students. But it also includes development of application and evaluation of systems and techniques in the field of education. The scope of educational technology improves aims and purposes in education, selection of media and resources; managing the resources etc. We can conclude that ET is an effective tool for teachers, researchers, students and educational administrators.

Latest conceptions

Latest conceptions are possible only due to computers, online learning, mobile learning, e-learning etc.

Positioning

ET takes Schools as a system to apply technology. According to the system, school's infrastructure such as building, teachers, furniture, are all inputs, while various other methods like strategies, techniques, latest applications along with the capability of students all are process in the system.

Technology in Engineering for education

Technology is widely used in the engineering sector of education. They produce FM radio, pen drives, CDs, tape recorders, computers, laptops, audio video gadgets, smart phones, and smart television all involved in the use of education. It should be borne in mind that engineering technology is different from educational technology. Programs should be properly selected to give the desired results in education.

Some people are of the opinion that educational technology will replace the instructors, coaches or teachers. This is clearly a myth grounded in absence of appropriate information. Educational technology can never replace a teacher. The teacher has a critical role to play in the teaching and learning process. It's the teacher, who helps the student accomplish the desired learning outcome. ET simply aids the teacher in this process.

With the latest pandemic situation pan world, nothing could have been more interesting than the online teaching. Children have adapted very well to this new norm of teaching. Children

not only learn in a short span of time but also get entertained by their teachers. They are now more exposed to media than before. Days have passed, when children were not given smart phones due to a number of reasons listed by parents. Now they have to provide the children with smart phones, laptops, tablets or smart television for their online classes. If parents are smart, their children have become smarter with the use of technology for education. Online teaching from the Pre k to K 12 has become the new in thing of today's world.

As every change has its own advantage and disadvantages, similarly this online system also has its pros and cons. This passage will deal with the advantages of technology in the form of online teaching.

Advantages of online teaching-learning:

1. Uninterrupted learning:

Under any circumstances in and around, with the closure of schools, learning should go on. Thus education can be done online and can be uninterrupted. As due to formal education, children are exposed to all kinds of life skills.

2. Learning in the confines of home:

In case of lockdown position, children can remain in confines of their own homes and be safe, still learning can go on.

3. Exposure to Parents:

In schools, parents were not aware about the kind of teaching done by the teachers, their efforts with each and every child, the kind of motivation and teacher child involvement moments all was not observed by parents. During such situations, teachers are under the vigilance of not only child's parents but also their family members. In such exposures teachers are criticized to any extent. This is again an embarrassing moment for teachers. A good bond has developed between parent-child-teacher, which is very important in holistic development of children. Parents are equally involving in uninterrupted learning.

4. Technological knowledge and ability:

Children have become techno savvy; thus, technology has enhanced education. We must remember that Educational Technology is a method to achieve a result but is not an result in itself. Digital technology has become more accessible to students these days. In the pre-technological age, teachers had to use real objects and reach out through face-to-face communication with their students. This was done to explain the past, relate it to the present and connect to future. Thus, attempt to encourage thinking about the future. In the time of mechanical era, there was large scale production of goods, printing press was invented.

People used machine made goods; this solved many difficulties in life. Books could be printed and storing and revival of data became easier. During the age of electronics, availability and access to technological devices increased further more. There was use of radio, television and photographs improved opportunities for better quality teaching for teachers. In the digital world a whole new set of inventions were developed. Highly erudite communication tools were developed, including smart mobile phones, word processors, digital cameras, high-end software, information and communication systems were developed. Teachers can have an access to the textbooks through online databases or websites or listen to entire books as audio files on MP3players. Computers have been very useful in every aspect of teaching.

Factors that affect the Adoption of IT

Attitude to use IT.

Teaching through Educational Technology teaching has proved that, there are number of factors by which it has a deep impact on the professional lives of the educators. Research proves that the educators are not only influenced, but are adopting the methodology in their class rooms, with these technological tools. Other than this the quality of Information and Communication Technology resources, the will to accept the change and the basic knowledge to use IT are perquisites. Change is inevitable, instructor should have the willingness to accept, self confidence is of prime importance, required knowledge and his capability to imbibe the role of ICT in the process of teaching which evolves in learning process. He should have the required support for the technology and the acceptance from the community to use IT. Whereas training should be imparted effectively along with the personal development training and the required resources if IT. –Peeraer et al. recognized other aspects include access to computers, intensity of computer use, ICT skills and ICT confidence. Means et al. (2001) cited that factors, such as lack of self- confidence, lack of social and behavioral attitudes can influence technology execution in city schools.

According to Balsh et al, assistance and encouragement rendered on the behalf of school organization can be regarded as one of the most essential variable, which is significant in the reception of educational technology. They emphasized on the support on behalf of school organizations, support from organizations lacking strategy and arrangement in utilization of education technology (Balash, 2011). In 2008 Mueller emphasized on the educator's mental framework in the direction of figuring imperative and contended that the given factor is actually rather fundamental to the possibility of including

information and communication technologies in the various modules and methodologies of education teaching. (Muller, 2008). In case the argument is presented that educators are unhappy with technology it has been seen that in that situation point load desires from technology are observed. Nevertheless, putting aside the perspective of such educators, Naimova has pointed at the perspective of managers as one of the variables capable of influencing educational technology's appropriation. According to Naimova in case of managers if there is absence of support from their side, it can lead to delayed in the utilization of technology in the area of study hall Nazimova, Research and Collection of Data (Naimova, Factors affecting the implementation of instructional technology in the Second Language classroom, 2008).

The role of the artistic education

The role of the artistic education in framing the future masters. The instruction procedure is occupied with certain noteworthy viewpoints required by the craftsmanship wonder that relates straightforwardly to the otherworldly universe and reasonable universes, which incorporate ideas such: creation, instructive learning and correspondence. The parts of the aesthetic instruction animate and create innovative capacities, basic reasoning and creative energy, and refine the cognizance that will total the acquisitions in the scholastic school, yet in addition the achievement, with a huge effect in building up the reasoning of every tyke who wishes an expert masterful profession. The methods for the formal rationale and epistemology stress the majority of the judiciousness in the Science of instruction region, the backing for the intricacy - a valuable reasoning that prompts an interpretative technique and a calculated instrumentation, vital for the assessment of postmodern training. In this specific circumstance, the aesthetic culture - a noteworthy securing of masterful training turns into a factor of judgment which decides the understudies to be occupied with slow reports inside their way of life. An after effect of this procedure is the development of the capacity to fabricate their very own masterful culture, and in an irrefutably way, their very own pictures about workmanship, and with the assistance of the imaginative sign, their very own mental self portrait. In progressive phases of advancement, it is resolved the feeling of craftsmanship, the quality exhibitions errands, and the meaning of objectives and capacities essential for prevailing in the homeroom and past. The craftsmanship can reform and decide appreciation reports and assuagement between individuals, through a valid correspondence. It can likewise supply the essential qualities, group building capacities and the thankfulness emerging from the regard of elective perspectives, given by various societies and customs. The dynamic development of the phases of appreciation, and the capacity to act in connection with their own masterful aims assume a noteworthy job in the arrangement of creative reasoning, inspirations, language and social enthusiastic advancement. The avocation of this procedure lies accurately in the directions of the well-known condition of youngsters that offers a solitary culture, possibly specific qualities encircled to a phase that can obstruct the entrance to humankind, which the school is intermediating through its qualities and through

the proclaimed reasons for professional training. Through inspiring the kids and their contribution in learning, connecting with the representative correspondence, anticipating their imaginative change and building up their abilities and capabilities, the school advances the states of acculturation of a youngster and finds a spot for everybody in individuals culture, likewise by advancing connections and coinciding in open spaces. Working certain determinations of aesthetic substance in training, or in the arrangement of a specific educational masterful culture, includes explicit dimensions of association for a "field" of the creative practices, colleagues and mental activities, produced by the craftsmanship particularities. The decent variety of practices demonstrates especially known activities: drawing, playing instruments, composing sonnets. What characterizes those activities is their tendency: social practices are recognized from the logical ones through their conclusion and through the developed tasks/mental ramifications. As model, the act of playing the piano or violin, woodwind or container woodwind, requires the information of the console, strings, funneling, interpreting the music sheet Luminița Heliana Munteanu et al. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* demonstrating the melodic timber of the sounds, their blend and the whole structure. Then again, working on painting or figure involves decent information of the materials, folios, work instruments and the perception of imaginative systems of the specialists (a painter won't be keen on clarifying the shadows amid the day, however will accomplish a created light).

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